

EFFECTIVE ASPECTS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: In this article, taking into account the fact that at the present stage, when moving to teaching Russian as a foreign language, the idea arose to create textbooks that meet modern requirements based on the methods, methods, experiences of learning Russian, which have been used for decades, and the motivation of children and their skills in educational activities have changed greatly, new textbooks focus, opinions about the inclusion of project activities are described.

Key words: primary class, Russian language, training, science integration, Russian Language Teaching, information and communication technologies, reading comprehension, listening comprehension, the ability to express thoughts in writing and verbally. information, modern textbooks, phonetics.

Primary school is the most important stage in a child's life, and as the basis, foundation of the duration of continuing education, during this period the sphere of interaction of the child with the outside world expands, the child begins to learn different languages. Teaching foreign languages from a young age in the face of a happy life and the future of the younger generation, creating a motivational environment for mastering a foreign language through it, and organizing classes in the current information age with the help of information and communication technologies are a requirement of today's times.

A distinctive feature of the content of modern elementary education is not only the answer to the question of what the student should know (remember, reproduce), but also the formation of universal educational actions. An important condition for the development of children's interest, the need for independent

knowledge of the world around them, cognitive activity and initiative in elementary school - the creation of a developing educational environment that stimulates active forms of knowledge: observation, experiments, educational conversation, etc. The young student must have skills such as understanding and evaluating his thoughts and actions from the outside, relating the result of the activity to the goal, identifying knowledge and ignorance in order to develop external relations.

The need to establish a new educational system for schools with Uzbek and other educational languages is multi-level in nature and arises for several reasons. The previously used Russian language teaching methodology was aimed at another sociolinguistic situation. Over the past 25 years, the language environment has changed significantly, the Russian language has constantly surrounded children (the language of neighbors, signs on the street, broadcasts on radio and television), and this has ensured the quality of his learning.

In a limited language environment, learning Russian twice a week for 34 study weeks a year is certainly not enough to fully master it. Therefore, there was a need to develop a new concept of the tutorial. To solve this problem, efforts were made to regularly include all types of speech activity in the project activities and in each lesson.

This approach allows the teacher of the Russian language to include the methodology of the Russian language for children in his activities. In this, the entire system from Grade 2 to Grade 11 (a1.1, A1.2, A2.1, a2.2, A2.3, B1.1, B1.2, B1.3, B1+) is well developed and allows you to achieve high language results, which increases the competitiveness of school graduates in the field of Russian language proficiency in Uzbekistan.

Given the fact that in recent years the motivation of children and their skills in educational activities have changed a lot, new textbooks focus on the needs of children for language learning, including the content of classes includes game activities, science integration, project activities.

In modern textbooks, children's access to the field of computer communication is already reflected. New education standards projects imply that

younger students participate in Computer Communication by putting individual educational tasks that can be solved on the basis of ICT tools: conducting correspondence with peers that affect their interests; expressing their own thoughts, using non-verbal communication and visual tools to interpret other people's ideas.

At the present stage, when moving to teaching Russian as a foreign language, the idea arose to create textbooks that meet modern requirements, based on the methodology, methods, experiences of studying the Russian language, which have been used for decades.

Since September 2021, new methods of teaching in schools (in Grades 2) on a specially developed educational and methodological complex for these purposes (methodological manual for the teacher + textbook + notebook + audio discs) have begun to be introduced in Uzbekistan.

New textbooks of the Russian language are based on the national curriculum and are aimed at teaching the Russian language as a foreign language, it is necessary to develop the following skills: understanding reading, understanding listening and the ability to express thoughts in writing and verbally.

The development of textbooks was engaged in cooperation with the Russian State Pedagogical University named after Gertsen, the Republican educational center under the Ministry of public education. Textbooks offer the ability to listen to texts through the application. Audio texts in the textbook are designed to develop the skills of perception of Russian speech through hearing in students. There are also many visual materials in the new textbooks. This is done because visual perception has certain advantages.

Also, in each of the Russian-language textbooks from the 2nd to the 11th grade, many pictures were used for the visual perception of a new topic. Each textbook contains 2 Project works and a dictionary in 7 languages.

In the previous textbook, grammatical information is given, while exercises are performed, in the new textbook, he learns grammar and receives new additional information from the text given to him in addition. The new textbook, the language

of instruction in the Uzbek language, will greatly help students in the development of oral speech in the Russian language. The new textbook is useful and convenient not only for the student, but also for the teacher. Through these texts, the teacher receives additional information, during the lesson he works with the student not only in one direction, but also in several directions (writing, reading, listening, speaking). In this process, ICT tools and other methods are used together in one lesson.

What are the benefits of new textbooks in Russian?

1. The main course of the lesson (or a topic consisting of a sequence of lessons) is not a grammatical rule as before, but a text. In addition, texts can be different in subject, style (artistic, informational, journalistic, Popular Science, etc.) and form (hard text): infographics, tables, diagrams, etc.

2. Exercises are also developed on the basis of the topic of the text, and this is aimed at the formation of the following features:

- text comprehension skills;
- Text creation skills (written or oral);
- critical and creative thinking skills, as well as research activities;
- language rules.

3. The rules of the language to be studied are not given regularly (from phonetics and lexicology to morphology, syntax and stylistics) and are explained through texts. In most cases, the rules are given in a reduced form without the use of excessive terminology.

4. The lessons were based on a communicative theme, surrounded by a selection of text (dialogue) to match vocabulary and grammar. This text serves as the basis for the development of language skills (understanding read or heard text, oral or written communication) and the study of vocabulary and grammar.

Therefore, in the process of learning Russian as a foreign language, special attention is paid to the development of oral speech, the formation of written speech, the assimilation of monological and dialogical speech, as well as the development of all types of speech activity (listening, speaking, reading and writing). Targeted

formation of speech skills ensures recognition by schoolchildren as a universal educational activity.

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